

TECHNICAL DATA SHEET

PEBAX® MV 1074 SA 01

POLYETHER BLOCK AMIDE PELLET

PEBAX® MV 1074 SA 01 is a polyether block amide, a thermoplastic elastomer made of flexible polyether and rigid polyamide. This SA grade offers the highest quality. It is used in sport and consumer applications, especially when food contact compliance is requested. This hydrophilic grade, when extruded into either a thin film or laminated on to a substrate, offers excellent permeability to moisture vapor while remaining waterproof. PEBAX® MV 1074 SA 01 is an inherently dissipative polymer and can be dry blended or compounded with an isolative polymer to lower the surface resistivity of the final part.

TYPE

PEBA

MAIN APPLICATIONS

- FILM
- ANTISTATICS

DELIVERY FORM

- Pellets

TRANSFORMATION PROCESSES

- Injection Molding

RHEOLOGICAL PROPERTIES

PROPERTIES	TYPICAL VALUE	UNIT	TEST STANDARD
Shrinkage, parallel (t+24h)	0.7	%	ISO 294-4
Shrinkage, normal (t+24h)	1	%	ISO 294-4

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

PROPERTIES	TYPICAL VALUE	UNIT	TEST STANDARD
Flexural modulus, 23°C (73°F)	- / 80	MPa	ISO 178
Tensile modulus, 23°C (73°F)	97 / 80	MPa	ISO 527-1/-2
Stress at 50% strain, 23°C (73°F)	- / 10	MPa	ISO 527-1/-2
Stress at break, 23°C (73°F)	- / 30	MPa	ISO 527-1/-2
Nominal strain at break, 23°C (73°F)	- / > 700	%	ISO 527-1/-2
Charpy unnotched impact strength, 23°C (73°F)	No break / No break		ISO 179 1eU
Charpy unnotched impact strength, -30°C (-22°F)	No break / No break		ISO 179 1eU
Charpy notched impact strength, 23°C (73°F)	No break / No break		ISO 179 1eA
Charpy notched impact strength, -30°C (-22°F)	No break / No break		ISO 179 1eA
Hardness, shore D, 15 s	- / 38		ISO 868

* Dry / Cond

Dry: Dry As Molded (DAM) if pellet / Dry if powder.

Cond: Conditionned.

THERMAL PROPERTIES

PROPERTIES	TYPICAL VALUE	UNIT	TEST STANDARD
Glass transition temperature, 10°C/min	-40	°C	ISO 11357-1/-2
Melting temperature, 10°C/min	158	°C	ISO 11357-1/-3

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ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES

PROPERTIES	TYPICAL VALUE	UNIT	TEST STANDARD
Surface resistivity, 23°C (73,4°F)	- / 3.0E+9	ohm/sq	IEC 62631-3-2
Volumic (transversal) resistivity, 23°C (73,4°F)	1.5E+9 / 2.5E+7	ohm.m	IEC 62631-3-1
Dielectric Strength, 23°C (73,4°F)	- / 5	kV/mm	IEC 60243-1

* Dry / Cond

Dry: Dry As Molded (DAM) if pellet / Dry if powder.

Cond: Conditionned.

OTHER PROPERTIES

PROPERTIES	TYPICAL VALUE	UNIT	TEST STANDARD
Density, 23°C (73°F)	1.07	g/cm ³	ISO 1183-1
Water absorption, at equilibrium at 23°C (73°F) / 50%RH	1.4	%	ISO 62

PACKAGING

Available packaging:

- 25 kg / 55 lb bags
- 550 kg rigid containers

SHELF LIFE

Two years from the date of delivery, when stored properly (sealed bags, appropriate moisture, UV protection and temperature). For any use above this limit, please refer to our technical services.

PROCESSING CONDITIONS:

- Typical melt temperature (Min / Recommended / Max) - Injection Molding: 210°C / 240°C / 270°C (410°F / 430°F / 520°F)
- Typical mold temperature - Injection molding: 10-30°C (50-90°F)
- Drying time and temperature: 60-70°C (140-160°F) / 4-8 hours

SPECIAL CHARACTERISTICS

- Anti-static

REGIONAL AVAILABILITY

Asia Pacific, Europe, Latin America and the Caribbean, Middle East, Northern America

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